

THEORETICAL BASIS OF USING THE SYSTEM OF PRODUCT QUALITY AND ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY INDICATORS IN AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. The article considers the quality indicators of the product as one of the main tasks of the market economy, since the demand of consumers for quality products is increasing day by day, increasing and filling the domestic market with quality products produced by ourselves, and the export potential of our Republic. improvement works are analyzed.

Key words: economic efficiency, profitability, quality indicators, system, profit, material cost, enterprise activity, cultivated area, gross product, productivity.

INTRODUCTION. The issue of improving product quality and increasing its competitiveness is of great importance for the further development of the economy of our republic. In the production, supply and planning of high-quality products, it is necessary to be familiar with modern evaluation methods and standards of quality indicators. A number of practical works are being carried out to improve the quality of products. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, which became a member of the international ISO organization in 1992, the "Quality" system was introduced to fulfill the main requirements for metrology and standardization. It is important to improve the quality of the product and increase it.

It is known that product quality is formed during research and design, production and consumption in its life stages.

Quality is defined as a set of definitions or descriptions of the object and is a characteristic of satisfying the requirements, otherwise it is called the quality, the level of satisfaction of the consumer's demand. Quality is the sum of the positive indicators of the product or a set of criteria that determine the consumer characteristics of the product.

It is possible to add to the concept of "quality" the completeness and diversity of the assortment, because they are considered as one of the qualities of fully meeting the needs of consumers.

By improving the quality of the finished product, its shelf life will be extended, the cost and labor costs will be reduced, the competitiveness in the world market will increase, the economy of the enterprise will be improved, and the consumer's demand will be fully satisfied. That is why product quality is an object of planning and quality management at the state level. Also, improving the quality of the product leads to a decrease in the volume of product quality production.

The high quality of goods indicates the well-developed science, technology and technology in one or another production branch. Improving product quality and ensuring it is one of the urgent problems of today, because this task arises from the requirements of the

market economy or relations.

Many factors influence the quality of the product, and these factors are conditionally technical, organizational, economic and social factors. These factors are divided into objective and subjective factors.

Objective factors include more technical factors: product and construction, mechanization and automation of production, technical level of the production base, technical means of control, modern technology, etc.

Subjective factors include factors related to human activity - a person's ability, attitude to perform production tasks.

Technical factors include equipment equipment, the condition of control tools and technical documents, the quality of raw materials and semi-finished products, and the like.

Organizational factors include such factors as planned and uniform work, technical service and equipment repair, production culture, organization of work on a scientific basis.

Economic factors include forms of payment for labor, the amount of monthly salary, promotion of high-quality products and work, withholding of labor due to product unfitness, cost and low price factors.

Social factors include the selection of personnel, their placement, organization of training, psychological environment and educational work.

The main goal of every farm is to improve product quality. To fulfill this task, special attention should be paid to the management of the quality system. Controlling the systematic sequence of production processes by the head of the farm has a positive effect on the production result as well as the improvement of product quality.

The experience of the United States, one of the world's leading countries, shows that quality system planning is important for effective product quality management. The process of planning and managing the quality system provides an opportunity to improve the quality of the product by determining the level of risks and opportunities, checking the compliance of the process with the results of the calculation, identifying defects and taking necessary measures.

The modern concept of quality management was reflected in the second half of the 20th century in the form of continuous improvement of the PDCA quality system by E. Deming, in books such as "Quality, Productivity and Competitiveness" and "Out of the Crisis". In these monographs, Deming's philosophy known as "Rule 14" was included, and they formed the basis of Total Quality.

There is also an approach of European countries in deciding product quality. It includes such features as the existence of a legal basis for work related to quality management and prohibition, ensuring team participation in improving product quality, and developing promising strategic programs.

Economic efficiency represents the useful result obtained by the use of means of production and live labor or the result obtained per unit of total resources. When assessing this or that event or determining its dimensions, it is necessary to know the criteria of economic efficiency. In the conditions of the market economy, since every enterprise has complete economic and legal independence, its main goal is to fully and effectively use the resources assigned to it, and the more income and profit it receives per unit of these resources, the more competitive it is. will have so much advantage.

It is appropriate to use the net profit per unit of total farm expenses as the main

criterion of economic efficiency when evaluating the activity of a farm. The advantage of the net profit category is that it also reflects the quantity and quality of the product, in what market and in what condition it was sold, and how much material and period costs were saved.

To establish a livestock farm, it is required to have at least 30 conditional head of livestock. The following coefficients are used to convert types of livestock to the conventional main measurement unit.

Table 1. Coefficients of conversion of types of livestock to the conditional main measurement unit

Coefficient	Types of livestock
1,0	Cattle and horse
0,6	Young cattle
0,3	A pig
0,1	A sheep and a goat
0,025	In poultry

Source: O. Murtazaev, F. Ahrorov. Agricultural economics. T. 2017

Economic efficiency means how many soums worth of products are produced for one soum spent. So it is determined by the ratio of the profit from the sale of the produced product to the costs of its production. Based on this indicator, it is determined how much was spent for each product unit. An increase in these costs leads to an increase in the value of goods.

On this basis, a number of economic indicators are used to determine the level of economic development and efficiency. There are no clear boundaries in the theoretical interpretation of economic efficiency indicators. Therefore, the issue of determining the ratio of these indicators remains open. It is desirable to clarify this issue, to choose the most optimal solution as a starting point for the study and evaluation of economic efficiency. Based on the opinions and opinions of scientists who have conducted research on the methodology of economic efficiency evaluation until now, they can be conditionally divided into two groups. Scientists belonging to the first group believe that the criterion indicator of economic efficiency should be the only one. According to their opinion, this indicator has a general characteristic and should objectively and completely reflect the economic efficiency.

It is necessary to take into account the rations and type of feeding of agricultural animals, their feeding systems and production structure, the quality of feeds, their cost and the coefficient of beneficial effect.

For dairy cows, analyzes are made on the feeding period in the barn and in the pasture, two or three options are considered, and the most reliable one is selected. Evaluation of these options is performed according to the following indicators: average daily milk yield, kg; average annual milk yield from a cow, kg; 1s milk feed consumption; available digestible protein in feed unit, g; Concentrates spent on 1s milk, feed unit; the cost of the feed unit of the ration, soums; feed costs per head of cow, soums; The cost of 1 product is soum.

At the level of mechanization of the type of work, the efficiency of feeding cows in different ways is evaluated according to the following indicators: annual milk yield from a cow, kg; annual labor cost per head of cow and 1s of milk, person/hour; 1s feed cost for milk, feed unit; Capital investment instead of 1 livestock, soum; 1s milk cost, 1s net profit from

selling milk, soums; profitability of milk production,%.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. It is reflected in the works and lectures of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev on the research of issues related to improving the efficiency of production of livestock products in agricultural enterprises. Also, this issue was discussed by the economists of our republic, especially the economists-scientists of our republic, O.P. Umurzokov, O. Murtazayev, A.Kh. Toshkulov, A.A. Abdug'aniyev, J. Rashidov, A.A. Toshboyev, R.Kh. Ergashev, S. .Dehkanov, T.Qudratov, F.Jorayev's scientific works, study guides and textbooks were used in the preparation of the dissertation by analyzing their theoretical and practical aspects.

In the conditions of modernization of agricultural enterprises, the economic scientists of our country and foreign countries have conducted scientific and research work in various directions on the problems of improving the quality of production of livestock products, improving the organizational and economic mechanisms of effective organization of the industry, and development based on innovation.

RESULTS. The question of improving product quality and increasing its competitiveness is of great importance for the further development of the economy of our republic, including the livestock industry. In the production, supply and planning of high-quality products, it is necessary to be familiar with modern evaluation methods and standards of quality indicators.

Animal husbandry is a labor-intensive type of production, and the use of the latest advances in science and technology through the mechanization and automation of work processes is a clear way to increase production efficiency and profitability.

In the field of livestock development, work is being carried out to increase the gene pool of livestock breeds and increase meat productivity, and to introduce innovative technologies to expand the fodder base through the use of genetic methods. Innovative development of animal husbandry is first of all directly related to the intensification of production, as a result of the use of improved innovative techniques and technology, as well as new forms of production and labor organization, the effective and full use of available resources ensures an increase in labor productivity.

The following indicators are used in the economic assessment of animal husbandry: provision of a sufficient supply of animal husbandry products in accordance with the demand of the population; number and productivity of livestock per 100 forage area; Livestock productivity, costs per head of livestock; the amount of products grown per fodder unit; labor productivity and product cost.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, it can be noted that in the majority of livestock farms, with the establishment of industrial production of products, the production of products was separated from the replenishment of cattle herds. In such conditions, it is advisable to establish specialized enterprises engaged in the care of young animals left for milk and beef production and rearing.

In the intensive way of increasing the volume of production, attention is mainly focused on increasing product productivity, that is, the farm increases labor productivity by involving in the production of high-yielding seed varieties and scientific and technical achievements without changing the cultivated area. As a result, due to the increase in labor productivity, the cost of 1 unit of product decreases, and the volume of the product also increases.

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